

Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils

Deliverable D5.1

Joint species distribution model for soil fauna

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Abstract

Here, we have modelled the spatial distribution pattern of 40 earthworm and 190 collembola species in response to climate (temperature and precipitation) and habitat conditions (soil, land use and land use intensity). This deliverable is strictly connected with D5.2.

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Table of Contents

1	Introduction	4
1.1.	State of the art	4
1.2.	MINOTAUR WP5 initial objectives and expected deliverables	5
1.3.	MINOTAUR WP5 actual work.....	6
2	Species Distribution Model for soil fauna	7
2.1	Species Data	7
2.2	Driver Data	8
2.3	Modelling and projections	9
2.4	Limitations	10
3	Conclusions and future directions	12

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1 Introduction

1.1. State of the art

In light of the threats posed by global environmental change, soil biodiversity is receiving increasing attention ([Phillips et al., 2020](#), [Lavelle et al. 2022](#)). Recently, several studies have addressed the driving environmental factors that explain the distribution patterns of soil invertebrate species and the assembly of communities. These works mostly focused on earthworm ([Mathieu and Davies, 2014](#), [Rutgers et al., 2016](#), [Phillips et al., 2019](#)), while only a few works dealt with collembola mostly in the context of polar ecology ([Vega et al. 2021](#)).

The hierarchy of the driving environmental factors of earthworms vary with scale. The main abiotic factors driving earthworm species occurrences and community assembly are temperature and soil moisture ([Eggleton et al., 2009](#), [Eisenhauer et al., 2014](#)), resource availability especially for species with low mobility ([Barot et al., 2007](#)), as well as the physical and chemical soil properties, like soil texture ([Nuutinen et al., 1998](#)), pH ([Lavelle et al., 1995](#), [Decaëns et al., 2008](#)), and organic carbon content ([Palm et al., 2013](#)). Earthworms are also affected by land use ([Decaëns et al., 2008](#), [Falco et al., 2015](#)) and land management ([Pothoff et al., 2008](#), [Pelosi et al., 2014](#), [Frazão et al., 2019](#)). On the other hand, biotic factors include competition ([Abbott, 1980](#), [Jiménez et al., 2006](#), [Decaëns, 2010](#)) or facilitation ([Jiménez et al., 2012](#)) with other species as well as small-scale dispersal processes ([Decaëns et al., 2008](#), [Mather et al., 1988](#)). At the broader scales, climate along with phylogeographic history rule ([Brussaard et al., 2012](#), [Phillips et al., 2019](#)). [Mathieu and Davies \(2014\)](#) identified post-glacial dispersal processes as an important biogeographical filter in France.

The spatial patterns of species and the habitat preferences of earthworms have also been described using species distribution models (SDMs). Single species occurrences or abundances have been modelled from presence-absence or presence-only data using either mechanistic (process-based) or correlative methods. [Johnston et al. \(2014\)](#) used a process-based model that combines individual energy budgets, movement and soil profiles to predict the abundance and distribution of *Aporrectodea*

caliginosa (Savigny, 1826). Taking a correlative instead of a mechanistic approach, MaxEnt algorithm has been applied to predict the relative probabilities of occurrence of different clades within Hormogastridae, an endemic Mediterranean family (Marchán et al. 2016, Marchán et al. 2015). Last, Shartell et al. (2013) applied a Generalised Linear Model to predict the percentage cover of the exotic *Lumbricus terrestris* Linnaeus, 1758 in the Upper Peninsula of Michigan as a function of soil properties and landscape characteristics. In a multispecies setting, Schneider et al. (2016) used Boosted Regression Trees (BRT) (Elith et al., 2008) to predict the abundance of common species at the catchment scale in an agricultural system. They calibrated a BRT model for each species independently. BRT were also used in a similar context to model the abundance of the three ecological groups of earthworm (Bouché, 1977), using for each ecological group the abundance of the others as covariates to estimate inter-group interactions (Palm et al., 2013). Large-scale applications of distribution models at the community level mostly involved modelling the total biomass or the species diversity. The latter were investigated at the country-wide scale in France (Mathieu and Davies, 2014, Rutgers et al., 2016), at the continental scale in Europe (Rutgers et al., 2016) using Generalised Linear Models and at the global scale (Phillips et al., 2019) using Generalised Linear Mixed Effect Models. Fourcade and Vercauteren (2021) used BRT to describe patterns of taxonomic and functional diversity of earthworm in France, and their projections under future scenarii. Zeiss et al (2023) focused on the effects of climate on the distribution and conservation of commonly observed European earthworms.

1.2. MINOTAUR WP5 initial objectives and expected deliverables

As written in the proposal, the objectives of MINOTAUR WP5 were to model the spatial distribution patterns of soil fauna assemblages from the local to the wide scales in response to climate and habitat conditions, with earthworms as first study case. Based on the obtained data, we proposed to compute and map selected indicators and to use the model to compute projections of biodiversity under future climate scenarios. Depending on available datasets, we will test whether the model is robust enough to

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be applied (i) to earthworms in other biogeographical contexts and (ii) to other group(s). If necessary we will adapt the model to increase its applicability domain.

The expected deliverables were :

D5.1 Joint Species Distribution Model for soil fauna; Original due date M45 (Oct 2023)

D5.2 Maps of soil biodiversity current status; Original due date M45 (Oct 2023), revised due date in M57.

1.3. MINOTAUR WP5 actual work

It was initially planned that the work in WP5 would be based on data collected and harmonised from the literature (WP2) or collected within the project (WP3-4). Unfortunately, it was not possible to use Edaphobase (<https://portal.edaphobase.org/>) to deposit the data (as initially expected), so a database dedicated to MINOTAUR was created *de novo*. This has led to *de facto* delays in making datasets available for WP5, and in carrying out the expected work. An extension was requested and granted to enable WP5 work to be carried out later than planned.

A dataset on earthworms was extracted in May 2024 from a intermediate version of MINOTAUR database. However, to compensate for a possible lack of MINOTAUR-harmonised datasets, usable for WP5, alternative datasets had been explored and prepared with a view to carrying out the work of WP5 with external data. Then, the objectives of MINOTAUR WP5 were adapted to the available resources and time before the end of the project. Hence, **we have modelled the spatial distribution pattern of 40 earthworm and 190 collembola species in response to climate (temperature and precipitation) and habitat conditions (soil, land use and land use intensity)**. Based on the models, **we have computed and map the local species richness**, one of the most used and widely accepted community indexes. The task related to the computation of projections of biodiversity under future climate scenarios or change in land use (intensity) is ongoing but not yet finished. The species distribution models and the projections on maps were produced during the summer of 2024 thanks to a tight collaboration with the Laboratoire d'Ecologie Alpine (Grenoble, France) more particularly Marianne Tzivanopoulos and Wilfried Thuiller (CNRS).

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2 Species Distribution Model for soil fauna

2.1 Species Data

To assess the relative importance of distribution drivers in Europe for a comprehensive number of earthworm and springtail species, we combined several datasets to compile a database of observation records. The Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF, <https://www.gbif.org/>) was the main source of species observations in this study. For springtails, GBIF data were completed with observations from [Potapov et al. \(2024\)](#), and Edaphobase. For earthworms, species records were contributed by the MINOTAUR database (<https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/minotaur>) and the #Vers2022 earthworm survey project ([Gérard et al. under review](#)). Additional data were also obtained from Edaphobase and [Phillips et al. \(2021\)](#). To obtain a reliable taxonomic reference for springtails, all species names were matched against the global Collembola checklist (www.collembola.org), as suggested by [Potapov et al. \(2024\)](#). Earthworm taxonomy was primarily based on the updated checklist by [Misirlioğlu et al. \(2023\)](#).

To optimise the temporal matching between species and environmental driver data, only observations recorded between 2000 and 2022 were retained. A minimum observation coordinate precision of 1000 m was chosen as a compromise between the available precision of environmental driver and species data and scale at which invertebrates experience their environment. In some cases, datasets containing gridded atlas data were removed manually after visual inspection.

To exclude problematic records, we filtered species observations using the CoordinateCleaner R package ([Zizka et al., 2019](#)) for the following potential errors: zero coordinates, equal coordinates, coordinates assigned to biodiversity institutions or the GBIF headquarters and coordinates at sea. A custom reference was used to detect coordinates at sea based on the EUROSTAT country borders projected to WGS 84 and buffered at 1 km in QGIS 3.30.1. The other tests were performed with the default parameters. Two datasets (the MINOTAUR earthworm dataset and the [Phillips et al. \(2021\)](#) earthworm dataset) did not provide information on coordinate precision.

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For these datasets, coordinate precision was estimated by removing observations with less than 2 decimal digits of coordinate accuracy. The centroid test in the CoordinateCleaner package was also used to remove observations with coordinates assigned to the centroids of a given locality. Additionally, we excluded observations from the databases obtained at experimental sites manipulating local environmental conditions.

For each taxonomic group we calculated the sampling effort by 1 km x 1 km raster cell by counting the number of observations of species belonging to the group across all datasets. Duplicates were removed beforehand using the CoordinateCleaner package. For the rest of the analyses only one observation by a raster cell was kept.

2.2 Driver Data

To study the ecological niches of European soil invertebrates concerning climatic, soil and land-use conditions, we took advantage of recently developed fine-scale datasets with wide geographical coverage. Climatic data were obtained from CHELSA at 1 km² resolution for the 1991-2020 time period (Karger et al., 2017). Soil data were downloaded from SoilGrids 2.0 at 250 m x 250 m resolution (Poggio et al., 2021). Due to gaps in available soil data in urban areas, missing values were imputed in QGIS using Inverse Distance Weighting through GDAL with a 500-pixel search radius and 3 smoothing iterations. The weighted mean values of soil variables for the first 30 cm of soil were calculated by combining the values of the 0-5 cm, 10-15 cm and 15-30 cm with the trapezoid rule and aggregated using the mean.

Land cover and land-use intensity data for the European Union were obtained from Dou et al. (2021). For the remaining study area, we used GlobCover as a source of land cover data (http://due.esrin.esa.int/page_globcover.php). To combine the two datasets, land cover and land-use intensity were split into separate variables in the Dou et al. (2021) dataset. For example, the variable “low-intensity grassland” was split into two variables, “grassland” and “low-intensity”. The GlobCover dataset was aggregated to 1 km² resolution by considering a land cover type as present if it was present in at least one 300 m x 300 m subpixel.

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Variable selection was performed based on expert knowledge of the environmental drivers of species distributions and by excluding potential predictors with a correlation higher than 0.8. From the climatic data, the variables growing degree days (heat sum above 5 °C, gdd5), snow cover days (scd), temperature seasonality (bio4), annual precipitation (bio12), and precipitation seasonality (bio15) were selected. Soil variables included the proportion of clay particles in the fine earth fraction of the soil (clay), the proportion of silt particles (silt), soil organic carbon content (soc) and soil cation exchange capacity (cec). There were 3 categories of land-use intensity (low, medium and high) and 10 land cover classes (arable land, urban areas, permanent crops, grasslands, forests, wetlands, bare rocks, shrubs, glaciers, water bodies).

2.3 Modelling and projections

To map earthworm and springtail distributions across Europe, species distribution modelling was used through the Biomod2 pipeline. Only species with 25 presences or more and who had at least 25% of their total observations within the European Union were modelled. Because no information on species absences was available, background points were drawn for each species randomly with a probability of selection weighted proportionally to the sampling effort for the species taxonomic group in each pixel of the study area. This method performed the best in comparison to other background point selection methods tested. To describe the whole niche of the species, the models needed to be calibrated on observations from Europe but also northern Africa and western Asia (Russia). As land-use intensity data was not available for the later regions, we developed a protocol to randomly remove 5% of land-use intensity values from the locations of observations and background points in European pixels in order to avoid the models capturing biased information. To calibrate species ecological niches, an ensemble of models was used with the following algorithms: Generalised Linear Models (GLM), Generalised Additive Models (GAM), down-sampled Random Forests (RF) and gradient boosting (XGBOOST). Model parameters were tuned and model performance was evaluated using spatial block cross-validation based on the True Skill Statistic (TSS) and Boyce Index with a block size varying from 10 km to 100 km depending on the number of observations.

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For species with less than 50 observations, random 5-fold cross-validation was used. In total 5 sets of background points and 5 cross-validation folds were used per model algorithm for a total of 100 models by species.

To project the current distributions, the models were used to produce ensemble committee averaging and weighted mean predictions. Models with a TSS validation score lower than 0.4 or two standard deviations less than the average TSS across all models calibrated for a given species were excluded from the ensemble projections. Moreover, the TSS was used to identify the threshold to filter predictions and produced binary distribution maps for each species. The coefficient of variation of the ensemble was also projected for each species as a measure of prediction uncertainty.

2.4 Limitations

Because of the limited number of observations available for certain species and the fact models do not account for species evolutionary history, distributions are at times overpredicted. A potential solution would be to constrain model predictions based on expert knowledge of species ranges such as IUCN maps. For taxa lacking this information, GBIF observations at large scale (e.g., 50 km) could be crossed with biogeographical region boundaries. Predictions within biogeographical areas with few or no observations could be downweighed using a penalization threshold. Another limitation is that stacking binarized distribution maps produced from species distribution models can lead to overestimation of species richness as species interactions and the local carrying capacity are not considered. Finally, although the selection of background points was controlled to counterbalance the unequal sampling effort of observations in space, this correction may not have been completely successful to eliminate all bias.

Results

Results of the models have been projected onto 1 km² grid maps. The spatial distribution pattern of 40 earthworm and 190 collembola have been gathered in two pdf files “Report_v1_collMaps.pdf” and “Report_v1_ewMaps”. The scale on the right side of the figures is graduated from 0 to 1000 per thousand and represents the probability of occurrence of a species in a 1 km² pixel. ‘Probability of presence of a

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species in a pixel' corresponds to the sum of models out of 1000 that have 'voted' whether the species is present or not. So 1000 means that all the models consider the species to be present in a location, and 0 means that no model considers it to be present (probability 0). At 500, roughly half the models consider the species to be present and the other half consider it to be absent. One has to keep in mind that 100 models were calibrated per species but not all were retained in the final set, depending notably on the number of observations. The more data, the more accurate the model, for instance 96 models were retained for *Al. chlorotica* or *Ap. longa* (1589 and 860 occurrences in the dataset), 92 models for *Ap. limicola* (108 occurrences) or 59 models for *Dendrobaena byblica* (28 occurrences).

Figure 1. Probability of presence for *Allobophora chlorotica*, shown as an example of species distribution model projections. The colors represent the proportion (out of 1000) of models that predicted the species to be present. Grey areas indicate regions where only a very small number of models predicted the presence of the species, suggesting low confidence in its occurrence.

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3 Conclusions and future directions

Understanding the drivers of soil fauna distribution is a prerequisite to predict their trajectory in response to the ongoing global changes, as well as to estimate the spatial emergence of their contribution to ecosystem functioning. So far, most studies used single species distribution models involving a limited number of widespread taxa or aggregated indicators such as biomass or richness, irrespective of the species identities. Studying each species separately using dedicated SDMs is time-consuming and unfeasible for species with few available observations due to their intrinsic rarity or to insufficient sampling effort. Modelling species distributions, rather than just community indices, will enable us to map not only species distributions but also the average trait values, the distribution of ecological categories, and the full spectrum of diversity within assemblages—taxonomic, functional, and phylogenetic. These additional analyses are currently underway using the models now available.

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